

Is language teaching in language schools influenced by research? An investigation into Chinese EFL teachers' conceptions

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This study explored the perceptions of L2 research held by English as a foreign language (EFL) teachers in Mainland China, along with their research engagement. Online questionnaires were completed by 55 teachers and four individual interviews were conducted online. Results showed that teachers perceived research as the collection of objective, quantitative data involving a large number of participants with results being statistically analysed and publicly shared. Teachers also showed a moderate level of L2 research engagement. Lack of time was the main reason given by teachers who had low research engagement while overseas study experience outside Mainland China was found to be related to higher levels of research engagement. Overall, the study contributes to a better understanding of the factors that influence L2 teachers' research engagement to ultimately be able to promote research activity in the teaching community.

Keywords: EFL; English Language Teaching; Perceptions of Research; Research Engagement; Teacher Research

1. Introduction

Does academic research reach its intended audience? An article by Biswas and Kirchherr (2015) titled "Prof, no one is reading you" presented the general limited exposure of academic papers to the public in which it mentioned that on average each peer-reviewed journal article was read by less than 10 people and 82% of the humanities articles and 32% of the social science articles were never cited. Does this disconnection from academia also apply to language teachers? Nassaji (2012) found English language teachers from Canada and Turkey seldom read research even though they had free access to it. Marsden and Kasprovicz (2017) in the United Kingdom also identified a lack of communication between researchers and foreign language teachers leading us to think that perhaps it is necessary to learn more about teachers' conceptions

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of research, their motivations for reading and conducting research themselves or their reasons for not doing so. Some scholars such as Nation (2018) or Cook (2009) see the connection between L2 research and language teachers as essential and expect teachers to apply academic evidence to their pedagogy.

Nevertheless, there seem to be obstacles in communication between teachers and researchers. For example, many of the empirical studies in *TESOL Quarterly* do not provide practical, pedagogical suggestions for teachers anymore (Han, 2007), and there seems to be a trend in the field of applied linguistics to become more theoretical as well as professionalized (Kramsch, 2015). The current study is interested in examining the connection between L2 research and practising English language teachers in language schools in Mainland China, where this relationship has been little investigated. The study is meant as an extension to Borg's (2009) seminal work on teachers' conceptions of research and research engagement and is meant to contribute to a better understanding of the gap between research and teaching as denounced by scholars such as Mckinley (2019), Medgyes (2017) or Ellis and Shintani (2013) to cite a few.

2. Background

A number of studies conducted with language teachers have been able to investigate their conceptions of L2 research and their views on its usefulness. Using questionnaires and interviews, Borg (2009) investigated how teachers from different countries perceived research. The results revealed that teachers had a traditional perception of research associated with objectivity, hypothesis testing, large samples, statistics and academic outputs. A more recent study by Banegas (2018) confirmed a traditional perspective of L2 research by teachers who also viewed objectivity as the key to good research. Through in-depth interviews with language teachers, Sato and Loewen (2019) found that their conception of research was relatively in line with SLA researchers' practices because teachers mentioned learning processes in their definitions on L2 research.

Findings regarding teachers' views on the usefulness of L2 research are not clear-cut. While the Canadian and Turkish English teachers who responded to a questionnaire in Nassaji (2012) believed SLA research to be beneficial to strengthening their pedagogy, they also felt that their own teaching experience was more useful for their teaching than the knowledge they could gain from SLA research. Other studies have also reported teachers questioning the practical function of using research in their teaching (Bas & Kivilcim, 2017; Kutlay, 2013) as well as showing little acceptance or understanding of the discourse that was used by the research community (Bartels, 2003). The difficulty in understanding the L2 research discourse might explain the findings in

Kamiya and Loewen (2014) where an ESL teacher's views on 'corrective feedback' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2010, 2023a) were hardly affected after reading and discussing three research articles on the topic. The fact that teachers tended to validate research based on how well they could integrate it into their teaching experience and less on the strength of empirical evidence of a study might also explain teachers' mixed feelings about the usefulness of L2 research.

In addition to examining teachers' conception of research, Borg (2009) also analysed teachers' research engagement in his study and defined it as both engagement in research (i.e., by doing it) as well as engagement with research (i.e., by reading and using it). The study showed that many of the respondents of the questionnaire reported moderate to low levels of reading and doing research. Lack of time, lack of knowledge, and little access to materials were reported to be the main reasons for not engaging in reading or conducting research.

Later studies have followed that are based on national samples such as Nassaji (2012) involving ESL teachers in Canada and EFL teachers in Turkey, Marsden and Kasprowicz (2017) involving modern language teachers in the UK, Banegas (2018) based on English teachers in Argentina, and Vu (2020) based on ELT lecturers in Vietnam. In line with Borg, Nassaji (2012) found that very few teachers stated that they read research articles and provided similar reasons (lack of time, difficulty of research articles) for not making more use of research. They also stated a lack of interest and prioritizing teaching experience over the knowledge they could gain from research as being more relevant to their teaching practices. In addition, differences were also observed between ESL teachers in Canada and EFL teachers in Turkey with fewer ESL teachers reading research articles 'often' and more of them showing a lack of interest in conducting research. Another interesting observation about reading research was made by Marsden and Kasprowicz (2017) whose modern language teachers reported having more exposure to research via professional association publications and events than via research journals. Banegas' (2018) work, like the present study, is an extension of Borg's study. The Argentinian EFL teachers in that study expressed levels of research engagement that were not too different from those obtained by Borg (2009). Factors such as teachers' working conditions or whether they had part- or full-time jobs helped explain teachers' levels of engagement. Teachers also tended to identify themselves as 'just teachers' and saw little direct benefits to engaging in or with research. An issue of identity together with some of the difficulties in engaging with research that was portrayed in Banegas' (2018) or Borg's (2009), based on a sample of teachers working at different levels of education, were also present in Vu's (2020) examination of ELT university lecturers in Vietnam, a site where research was supposed to be an inherent part of teachers' jobs. Together, these

studies showed that language teachers in different contexts and countries tended to have a conventional conception of research and experience multiple constraints in relation to L2 research.

Since the Chinese government introduced the economic policy “Reform and Opening-Up” in the 1980s, the connection between Mainland China and most of the world has strengthened (Bolton & Graddol, 2012). The English learner population has surged and the demand for English language instruction has increased significantly over the past decades (Adamson, 2002) in part as a result of English becoming part of China’s College Entrance Examination in 1984 as a compulsory subject (Feng, 1999). According to a 2020 news article by Li in *People’s Daily online*, it was estimated that nowadays 400 million Chinese people are learning English and 703,500 students studying abroad (Li, 2020).

In this context, investigating Chinese teachers’ conceptions of research and their actual engagement was important to understand how the connection between research and teaching practice could be eventually strengthened. Several studies have been published that have an exclusive focus on Chinese teachers of English outside the primary and secondary school sectors in connection to their L2 research engagement. In these studies, several aspects related to teacher engagement with research have been examined such as teachers’ conceptions of research and their perceived competence to perform tasks in research. Both of these factors are relevant because low levels of research efficacy and teachers’ misconceptions of L2 research could restrict teachers’ research engagement (Xun, 2018). For example, Borg and Liu (2013) reported some college English teachers in China not being clear about what research was and felt ill-prepared to conduct the type of research that they were expected to produce in their institutions. For many teachers in China, this type of research was associated with a positivistic paradigm and the idea that research was inherently abstract and theoretical (Gao & Chow, 2012; Han, 2021). At the same time, some Chinese teachers in higher education have been reported to feel a tension between this experimental type of research and a more practical type of research that would be more relevant to the classroom and their own professional development (Borg & Liu, 2013). In addition, college English teachers in China also tend to feel a tension between the little support to engage in research that they receive from their institutions and the pressing need to conduct publishable research for promotion (Nana and Jing, 2017). Teachers across different studies (Borg & Liu, 2013; Nana & Jing, 2017; Wang & Han, 2011; Xu, 2014) viewed publishing as one of the major barriers (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023b) that they encountered due to the existence of a black publishing market, the need for social connections in publishing and the disproportion between the number of English teachers needing to publish and the small number of available journals. In sum, college English teachers in

China were likely to feel pressed to engage with research in their institutions and as a result, may feel discouraged. As such, the present study aims to get further insights into this complex situation some teachers may find themselves in by focusing on language schools in China, including language schools that are part of a university.

Part of the rationale for the present study is in response to Borg's call for further empirical research into teacher engagement in different contexts. It is also an extension of Borg's (2009) seminal work involving teachers from 13 countries (including Mainland China). As in Banegas (2018), we are going to use the survey Borg initially developed to allow for later comparison of results. This same survey is used as a secondary instrument by Gao et al. (2011) to explore primary school English teachers' conceptions of research in China, and it is the main instrument in Borg and Liu (2013) to study Chinese college English language teachers' research engagement. Unlike Borg and Liu, we focus on both teachers in language schools that are part of a university, and teachers from independent language schools and explore an association between teachers' individual and contextual variables and their research engagement. The fact that our sample is quite heterogeneous justifies the exploration of these associations, which to our knowledge, have not been explored in previous research. The following 4 questions will be discussed:

1. What are Chinese EFL language schoolteachers' conceptions of ELT research?
2. How do Chinese EFL language schoolteachers evaluate the research culture in their places of employment?
3. To what extent do Chinese EFL language schoolteachers read and conduct ELT research?
4. To what extent are Chinese EFL teachers' individual (e.g., age, teaching experience) and contextual variables (e.g., type of institution, learners' level of proficiency) associated with their research engagement?

3. Method

3.1. Participants

The current study used a sample of 55 ($N = 55$) Chinese EFL teachers working in both private and public language schools. Informed consent was received from all the participants before the study. The snowball sampling procedure was used to reach Chinese EFL teachers from intermediate to advanced English proficiency, ensuring they were able to comprehend the questionnaire in this study via a popular Chinese social media (*WeChat*). There were 43 females and 12 males. Table 1 shows that nearly half of the participants were aged between 26-30.

Most of them had between 1 and 9 years of teaching experience. The highest qualification respondents had earned related to ELT were a master's or PhD degree (45.4%) followed by a bachelor's degree (27.3%), a Certificate or Diploma (25.4%), or Other (1.8%). Regarding staying abroad, 27% of them had studied outside Mainland China in locations such as Australia, Canada, Hong Kong, Spain, the United States of America, the United Kingdom, and Japan. Forty-three of the teachers indicated they were working in private schools and 12 in state schools. Twenty-one of the teachers were working for language schools that were a part of a university. Over half (63.6%) of the teachers were teaching students aged between 13-19, and 65.5% had students at an intermediate level. In response to what linguistic skills (reading, listening, speaking, and writing) they were teaching, most teachers (69.1%) were teaching a reading class.

Of the 55 participants, 4 Chinese EFL teachers working at private language schools were also interviewed. Two of these teachers were working in the city of Beijing and the other two in Liaoning, and the reason they were chosen was because they were representative of the average profile of language teachers in these cities: teachers with only a few years of teaching experience and limited training as EFL teachers (see Table 2).

Table 1

Participants' Age Range

Age group	N	Percent
20-25	11	20.0%
26-30	27	49.1%
31-35	11	20.0%
35+	6	10.9%
Total	55	100%

Table 2

Interviewees' Background Information.

Interviewees	University degree	Certification	Experience
Angela	English studies (B.A.)	TKT	6 years
Jane	English studies (B.A.)	---	5 years
Edward	Manufacturing (B.A.)	TKT	4 years
Nicole	Teaching Chinese as a Foreign language (B.A.)	---	4 years

At the time of the study, two of the participants, Edward and Nicole (all participants' names are pseudonyms to protect their anonymity), had recently changed from full-time to part-time jobs, while the other two teachers, Angela and Jane, were working full-time at different private language schools in Beijing. Edward had earned a Teaching Knowledge Test (TKT) certificate for teaching English after graduating with a manufacturing major from university and had been teaching TOEFL reading for about 4 years as a full-time teacher at a private language institution. When the interview was conducted, he had quit the language school to open his own small English school. Nicole was

enrolled in a master's degree in professional accounting at an Australian university when the interview was conducted and was receiving instruction online while still living in China. She had previously majored in 'Teaching Chinese as a Foreign Language' (CFL) as an undergraduate and had been teaching IELTS reading and vocabulary for four years as a part-time job. When the interview was conducted, she was still teaching English part-time. Angela had majored in English studies at university and had earned a TKT certificate after which she started teaching English. Angela had been teaching TOEFL listening and IELTS listening for 6 years. Jane had also majored in English and had been teaching TOEFL writing and IELTS writing for 5 years.

3.2. Instruments

Following Borg (2010), structured questionnaires were used as the primary instrument in this study in combination with semi-structured interviews. The use of these two instruments allowed us to capture both 'etic' and 'emic' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2019) perspectives. The questionnaire was adapted from Borg (2010) and kept in English as all participants of the study had an adequate level of English proficiency. Other questionnaires on teacher engagement were discarded because they did not include a specific section on the perceptions of research as Borg's (2010)' study did.

Out of the 6 sections in the original questionnaire, sections 1 (Research scenarios judgment), 3 (Research culture), 4 (Reading research), and 5 (Doing research) were kept identical as they met the goal of the current study. Section 2 (Characteristics of good quality research) was removed since it overlapped with section 1. In the research scenarios section participants were prompted to judge whether a number of scenarios ($n = 10$) could be defined as research by responding to a 4-point Likert-scale ranging from 'Definitely not research' to 'Definitely research'. In the research culture section on the teachers' workplaces, participants had to express their level of agreement with 9 statements on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 'Strongly disagree' to 'Strongly agree'. The questions in sections 4 and 5 aimed to investigate participants' frequency of reading and conducting research with multiple-choice and checkbox questions. While one of the strengths of Borg's (2010), questionnaire is that it deals with a range of dimensions of research engagement and has a clear layout, the term 'research' is not defined, and it is possible it was interpreted differently by respondents when answering statements such as 'How frequently do you research yourself?' or 'Teachers read published research'.

To elicit more accurate and in-depth answers, four semi-structured interviews were carried out online. The interview questions included eight questions on the same topics as the questionnaire.

3.3. Procedure

The online questionnaire was distributed to Chinese EFL language schoolteachers through social networks, and it was available for four weeks. Teachers who finished the questionnaire were then asked whether they would like to take part in an interview. All of the interviews were video- and audio-recorded with the participants' permission. Participants were interviewed individually, with each interview lasting about 40-60 minutes. The four interviews were conducted in Chinese and then were transcribed for analysis. Interviews were orthographically transcribed in full and thematically analysed (Sato & Loewen, 2019). Interview data were used to elaborate and illustrate the quantitative analysis of the questionnaire.

4. Results

Research question 1

In section 2 of the questionnaire, participants were asked to decide to what extent they thought the 10 scenarios described could be defined as research. The responses to the 10 scenarios were included in table 3 (below).

Table 3

Assessment of 10 Scenarios (1= Definitely not research; 2=Probably not Research; 3= Probably research; 4=Definitely research)

scenarios	1		2		3		4	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1. A teacher keeping a diary	10	18.2%	12	21.8%	21	38.2%	12	21.8%
2. A teacher analysing video recordings and learners' work	3	5.5%	14	25.5%	22	40%	16	29.1%
3. A teacher writing an essay about grammar teaching	9	16.4%	17	30.9%	21	38.2%	8	14.5%
4. 500 teachers' questionnaires analysed with statistics	2	3.6%	12	21.8%	16	29.1%	25	45.5%
5. Two teachers conducting class observation	4	7.3%	9	16.4%	28	50.9%	14	25.5%
6. A teacher comparing 2 teaching methods	5	9.1%	8	14.5%	17	30.9%	25	45.5%
7. A headmaster writing a report	5	9.1%	15	27.3%	16	29.1%	19	34.5%
8. 5 students' feedback	8	14.5%	17	30.9%	20	36.4%	10	18.2%
9. A teacher trainer writing an article about training	7	12.7%	10	18.2%	24	43.6%	14	25.5%
10. A head presenting his study	4	7.3%	13	23.6%	12	21.8%	26	47.3%

Scenarios 4, 6, and 10 were rated highest as examples of 'Definitely research'. In general, most of the participants understood research as the quantitative analysis of data gathered from a large participant pool to ensure objectivity in the analysis. The university lecturer in scenario 4 distributed questionnaires to

500 teachers, investigating computer usage in language teaching, which was analysed statistically and then published. Scenario 6 described a teacher who wanted to improve her strategies for teaching vocabulary by testing 2 different teaching methods with 2 different classes, and she used the one that worked best. In scenario 10, in order to know whether teachers liked a new coursebook, the head of an English department asked them to complete questionnaires and presented teachers' responses to all staff.

Scenarios 1, 3, and 8 were rated highest as examples of 'Definitely not research'. In contrast to scenarios 4, 6, and 10, in this case, there were 2 scenarios that did not include any data (scenarios 1 and 3) and one scenario with a very small sample (scenario 8), which would preclude statistical analyses. Scenario 1 described a teacher who had improved her pedagogy by taking notes in her diary. The teacher in scenario 3, who was an MA student, wrote a review article in which she talked about grammar teaching. In scenario 8, a teacher distributed a feedback form to 30 students and 5 students returned it the following day, so she made pedagogical decisions based on those 5 responses.

During the interviews, the 4 teachers were asked how they perceived ELT research. Both Angela and Edward mentioned that they had been asked this question in the TKT test. Angela described research as a process for addressing difficulties:

First, there is the phenomenon, and then there is a problem that needs to be studied. Then you set up a similar scene and simulate it. And then you look at the results and come to a conclusion.

Edward defined research with a specific language teaching example:

First of all, you have to spend a lot of time to produce objective data to support the research you are doing. If you come to a conclusion, it has to be something that is generalizable. For example, I used one certain teaching method and helped 70-point TOEFL students to get 90-point. If the method cannot be applied to most of the students, then it is not successful research.

Jane gave a more general answer in her attempt to define research:

Research could be divided into the study of people and the study of objects. Doing research with people is like interviewing people, so researchers need empathy. The results are relatively subjective, which is biased sometimes. However, the study of objects, such as plants, is simpler than the study of people.

Nicole required some hints when being asked to define research. After the prompt, she believed that research could be a chemistry experiment as well as a questionnaire. The 4 participants defined ELT research in their own way. Additionally, Edward was the only one who focused on ELT specifically, claiming that research should produce data that could be applied to most teaching contexts. The other 3 interviewees failed to build any connections between research and linguistics or English language teaching. Rather, they tended to associate research with quantitative, generalizable studies related to fields such as chemistry or physics.

4.2. Research question 2

Section 3 of the questionnaire aimed at investigating to what extent Chinese EFL teachers were encouraged to read and conduct research in their work environment. Table 4 summarized all their responses.

Table 4
Research Culture (1= Disagree; 2= Don't know; 3= Agree)

Research culture	1		2		3	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
1 Teachers do research themselves	10	18.2%	5	9.1%	40	72.7%
2 The management encourages teachers to do research	11	20.0%	8	14.5%	36	65.5%
3 Teachers feel that doing research is an important part of their job	13	23.6%	5	9.1%	37	67.3%
4 Teachers have access to research books and journals	10	18.2%	6	10.9%	39	70.9%
5 Teachers have opportunities to learn about current research	9	16.4%	8	14.5%	38	69.1%
6 Teachers talk about research	13	23.6%	9	16.4%	33	60.0%
7 Teachers are given support to attend ELT conferences	9	16.4%	7	12.7%	39	70.9%
8 Time to do research is built into teachers' workloads	11	20.0%	7	12.7%	37	67.3%
9 Teachers read published research	10	18.2%	11	20.0%	34	61.8%

As Table 4 shows, the overall response to this section was positive. Most of the respondents agreed that teachers in their schools shared a good research culture. However, the 4 interviewees disagreed, stating that they did not have a satisfying research culture in their places of employment. Edward pointed out that the school valued the sales and marketing departments more than the teaching department:

We don't have a research culture, the core of the language school is not the teaching department, but the sales and marketing department. There is

not enough attention paid to the teaching department, though they occasionally send teachers to attend training programs.

Jane also emphasized the importance of the marketing department:

The marketing department should be in charge of this (here "this" refers to collecting data for conducting ELT research). They have first-hand information from students and parents. As teachers, we don't have pools to find enough participants and collect data.

Angela expressed that, as the head at her language school, she was not aware of the best way to promote research culture:

We have a weak research culture. We neither read nor discuss research. Instead of calling it (here "it" refers to weekly group meetings) a research seminar, I would say it's more like a workshop where teachers communicate their teaching experience. If you hadn't reminded me today, I would not have thought of teaching and conducting research in such a way.

4.3. Research questions 3 and 4

In section 4, participants were asked how frequently they read scientific publications. Just over half of the participants (56.4%) revealed that they read research sometimes; 30.9% said they rarely did so and 10.9% often; only one teacher said that she never read research.

Teachers who reported reading research 'sometimes' or 'often' (a total of 37 teachers) described the sources that they had access to (from most frequent to least frequent): web-based sources of research (64.4%), books (49.1%), academic journals (49.1%), professional journals (36.4%), professional magazines (29.1%), newsletters (18.2%), and others (8.9%). When these teachers were asked to what extent reading research influenced their teaching, their answers were: no influence (3.6%), slight influence (21.5%), moderate influence (40%), fairly strong influence (14.5%), and strong influence (1.8%). Additionally, 40% of those who said that they read research 'sometimes' or 'often' claimed that reading research had a moderate influence in their classrooms. As the only interviewee who read research sometimes, Edward claimed that reading academic articles could confirm his pedagogy and allow him to be more confident:

When you read so many researchers saying the same thing, it makes you feel more confident in your teaching methods. This is the most useful point.

In order to test the relationship between participants' research reading habits and their individual characteristics such as age, training, teaching experience, etc. (see table 5), a number of *chi*-square tests were run. As table 5 shows, only the relationship between reading frequency and overseas study experience (here 'overseas study experience' refers to teachers who had studied outside Mainland China) was close to reaching statistical significance, although it was still non-significant. Teachers with overseas study experience tended to read more research than those without this type of experience.

Table 5
Relationship Between Research Reading Habits and Teachers' Individual and Contextual Variables

	χ^2	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Gender	.003	1	.960
Age	2.174	3	.537
Teaching experience	1.629	4	.804
Qualification	3.713	5	.591
Overseas study experience	3.524	1	.061
Institution type	.557	1	.455
Part of university	.266	1	.606
Students' age	2.745	2	.253
Students' level of proficiency	2.676	2	.262
Teach reading	2.295	1	.130
Teach listening	.223	1	.637
Teach speaking	.223	1	.637
Teach writing	.231	1	.631

Table 6
Reasons for Not Reading Research

Reasons	%
I do not have time	21.8%
I do not have access to books and journals	20%
I find published research hard to understand	20%
Published research does not give me practical advice for the classroom	16.4%
I am not interested in research	9.1%
Other reasons	3.6%

The other teachers ($n = 18$) who stated that they 'barely' or 'never' read research were required to identify the reasons for not reading research. The reasons are listed in Table 6. Note that participants were allowed to choose more than one of the reasons listed. A shortage of time was the main reason

given (21.8%). What followed next was a lack of access to books and journals (20%) and having trouble with understanding published research (20%).

The three interviewees that reported not reading research said that they would love to know and read more about research, but they lacked access to academic articles, as Angela put it:

I believe that language teaching research would be useful, but neither I nor other teachers know where to find this research. People don't know that there are research articles out there about English language teaching.

Section 5 of the questionnaire concentrated on the extent to which teachers conducted research themselves. Approximately half of the participants (56.4%) revealed that they conducted research 'sometimes' or 'often'.

Table 7 shows the reasons chosen by participants to conduct their own research. When asked about the reasons why they carried out research, participants were able to choose more than one of the reasons listed. As Table 7 shows, out of 31 teachers who reported doing research "sometimes" or "often", almost half of them (49.1%) did research for their professional development. Some teachers (32.7%) reported that they conducted research as part of a course they were taking; others (30.9%) reported the aim of improving their teaching methods. Another third of the teachers claimed that they carried out research in order to solve teaching problems. In general, most of the reasons why teachers claimed they carried out research showed that there was a relative concern among participants for professional development as well as for improving their teaching. Interestingly, no teacher was concerned with the fact that other teachers could learn from their research.

Table 7
Reasons for Doing Research

Reasons	%
Because it is good for my professional development	49.1%
As part of a course I am taking	32.7%
To find better ways of teaching	30.9%
To solve problems in my teaching	29.1%
Because it will help me get a promotion	25.5%
Because I enjoy it	23.6%
To contribute to the improvement of the school in general	20.0%
Because my employer expects me to	18.2%
Because other teachers can learn from the findings of my work	0%

There were 24 teachers who reported that they 'never' or 'hardly ever' did research. Again, when asked about the reasons why they did not carry out

research, they could choose more than one reason. As Table 8 shows, the main reasons given were lack of research background or training (30.9%), followed by lack of time (29.7%) and lack of somebody for support or advice (27.3%).

Table 8
Reasons for Not Doing Research

Reasons	%
I do not know enough about research methods	30.9%
I do not have time to do research	29.7%
I need someone to advise me, but no one is available	27.3%
Most of my colleagues do not do research	21.8%
My job is to teach, not to do research	20%
I do not have access to the books and journals I need	18.2%
My employer discourages it	12.7%
I am not interested in doing research	12.7%
Other teachers would not cooperate if I asked for their help	12.7%
Learners would not cooperate if I did research in class	1.8%

Table 9
Chi-square Distribution Table of Participants Experience Doing Research and Individual and Contextual Variables

	χ^2	df	Sig.
Gender	.662	1	.416
Age	2.245	1	.134
Teaching experience	.296	1	.587
Qualification	.355	1	.551
Overseas study experience	.111	1	.739
Institution type	.662	1	.416
Part of university	.008	1	.927
Students' age	7.359	2	.025*
Students' level of proficiency	6.355	2	.042*
Teach reading	2.307	1	.129
Teach listening	1.087	1	.297
Teach speaking	.246	1	.620
Teach writing	1.455	1	.228

Among the four interviewees, Jane was the only one with research experience when she was at university:

I once conducted research when I was an undergraduate. I did things such as group discussions and interviews based on teachers' requirements. I

haven't had a chance to do research since I started working, but I have been really interested.

The four interviewees, who reported little involvement in research, also mentioned that they had no professional research knowledge and that they did not have time to do research due to a heavy teaching load.

In order to test the relationship between participants' experience conducting research and other participants' variables (e.g., their age, teaching experience, etc.), a series of chi-square tests were run. As Table 9 (above) indicates, in terms of conducting research, only students' age and students' level of proficiency showed statistically significant differences: in this sense, teachers got significantly more involved in conducting research when they were teaching groups of older and/or higher proficiency learners.

5. Discussion

Regarding research question 1, based on the 10 scenarios described in section 2 of the questionnaire as well as responses from interviews, teachers tended to believe that research could be described as the collection of objective quantitative data in which a large number of participants are involved, and in which results are analysed statistically before being shared publicly (scenarios 4, 6 and 10). This means that their perception of research is close to the traditional theory of scientific research. On the other hand, teachers did not identify self-reflective practice in teaching (scenarios 1, 3, and 8) as research. These results are consistent with Borg's (2009) study, along with other studies (Banegas, 2018; Borg, 2007; Dörnyei, 2007; Kutlay, 2013). Teachers in Borg's (2009) study exhibited a tendency to choose scenarios 2, 4 and 6 as examples of research scenarios; on the other hand, scenarios 1, 8 and 9 were chosen as the least possible research scenarios. So, participants from both Borg (2009) and the present study consistently believed that scenarios 4 and 6, along with scenarios 1 and 8, are representatives of the closest scenarios to research and the least close to research respectively. There are two possible interpretations of this. The first one is that teachers believe that true research is exclusively restricted to fields such as physics or chemistry. On the contrary, for them, reflective teaching practice is considered a daily work routine as opposed to formal research. Another possible interpretation is that participants believe that research findings must be presented publicly, in line with Stenhouse (1981) who claimed that research for private purposes was not research.

There are different ways to define research, it should not be narrowed down to natural sciences alone. Research fields such as applied linguistics as well as language teaching have been ignored by one of the main potential consumers of ELT research, language teachers. The findings from the present study as well

as a similar study from the Chilean context (Banegas, 2018) may explain why 'not having access to academic articles' is rated second among the reasons for not reading research. For those who have little or no experience with research, it is natural that they cannot provide a clear definition of research. Furthermore, if teachers are not able to define ELT research well, and they are not aware of its advantages when facing teaching problems, they will tend to look for help from experienced teachers or teaching guidance (as suggested by the interviewees in the present study) instead of reading ELT research articles.

Regarding the second research question, which focused on research culture in the workplace, most participants in the present study claimed that they had a positive research culture in their place of employment, which was in line with Banegas (2018), Borg (2007), and Borg (2010). However, this was not in line with the participants' answers to other sections of the questionnaire, where they frequently reported a lack of access to books or journals as well as insufficient professional support as the main reasons for not reading or doing research. This implies that schools hardly provide technical support to teachers to foster their research engagement. The results from the interviews in the present study also confirmed this lack of positive research culture in institutions, since the focus of most schools is in sales and marketing. The four interviewees reported that, instead of having a research culture, they have a sales culture. Rather than giving financial support to teacher training and development, schools were willing to spend more money on advertisement and salaries among the sales staff.

Research question 3 focused on the frequency with which participants read or conducted research. A moderate research engagement was found. About 67.3% of the participants said that they read research 'sometimes' or 'often'. This is in line with Borg's (2009) study, in which 67.5% of the participants stated that they read research 'sometimes' or 'often'. The most common type of research they read was web-based, which exerted a moderate influence on their teaching. This can possibly be explained by the fact that free online journals and research databases are becoming increasingly accessible in China and worldwide. In terms of doing research themselves, almost 56% of the participants reported that they conducted research 'sometimes' or 'often'. This was consistent with Borg's (2009) findings again, where 54.6% of the participants stated that they conducted research 'sometimes' or 'often'. Furthermore, lack of time was given as the most influential factor for not reading or conducting research in both Borg's (2009) study and the present study. A possible explanation for this might be that teachers have extensive teaching hours in language schools. When teachers' schedules are fully booked (giving lessons from 8 a.m. to 8 p.m.), it is impossible for them to have time and energy to read or conduct research. Additionally, as most respondents claimed, the main reason for conducting research was professional development.

However, for most participants, 'professional development' was a synonym for 'getting a promotion' and not necessarily 'finding better ways of teaching' or 'solving teaching problems'.

Finally, research question 4 focused on the relationship between teachers' characteristics and their levels of research engagement. The findings from the present study showed that overseas study experience was slightly associated with greater research engagement in terms of reading research, although the relationship was only close to statistical significance. Further research should test the robustness of this relationship. In any case, participants' academic experience abroad was not significantly related to whether they conducted research themselves or not. Rather, it was the type of students that they had in class that motivated teachers to conduct research, as the findings from the present study showed that teachers conducted research when they were teaching groups of adult learners (instead of teenagers or young children) or when they were teaching advanced learners (instead of beginners or intermediate learners).

Participants' age or years of teaching experience did not show statistically significant differences in terms of research engagement either (neither reading nor doing research). Contrary to previous studies like Borg's (2009) study, participants in the previous study were relatively young (i.e., most participants were less than 35 years old) and had limited teaching experience (i.e., most participants had 1 to 9 years of teaching experience). On the other hand, in Borg's (2009) study, 60% of teachers ranged from having 10 to 25 years of teaching experience. Thus, the differences in terms of research engagement between younger and older generations, and more or less experienced teachers cannot be confirmed with the present data. Further research with a wider, more varied sample in terms of both age and years of teaching experience might confirm this relationship.

6. Conclusion

The present study provides an exploration of the conceptions that a group of Chinese EFL teachers have of research through qualitative data gathered through surveys and interviews. As a qualitative study, one of its limitations is the non-probability sample procedure followed. The limited number of survey respondents as well as the small number of interviews conducted (all of which took place with private school teachers) also conditions the generalizability of the findings in this study. The fact that the schools where the teachers worked were localized in Beijing and Liaoning also lowers the external validity of this work, given the diversity and size of the country. A larger more varied and systemic sample would have certainly provided a better picture of the whole teaching community. In any case, the present qualitative data can unfold

possible existing patterns and connections between teachers' conceptions and actual research and teaching practice that can inspire future studies. Further quantitative research with larger and more varied samples should confirm the patterns that can be hypothesized with the present qualitative data.

Understanding how English language teachers perceive ELT research is a prerequisite for encouraging their participation in research so as to promote research in applied linguistics. Hence, future studies should analyse the way teachers perceive research and whether they are willing to apply research findings to their classrooms. Also, there is a great need for research in language teaching to be conducted in Mainland China since the market for English learning and teacher training there has become an indispensable part of the global English learning industry.

Funding

This research was supported by grant 2020FI_B2 00179 from the Catalan Agency for Management of University and Research Grants.

Authors' Statement

Adiya Adiya contributed to the writing of sections 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 of this paper, Sara Feijoo also contributed to the writing of sections 3, 4, 5, and 6, and Elsa Tragant also helped in the writing of sections 1, 2 and 3.

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